

SOME LANGUAGE ELEMENTS IN THE CREATION OF OMON MATJAN

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Abstract The article analyzes the words characteristic of Khorazmlahja used in Amon Matjon's poems.

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Linguistics, which is considered one of the leading directions of anthropocentric linguistics, is a field that has emerged from the cooperation of linguistics, cultural studies, ethnography, psycholinguistics, and studies the interaction and influence of language with culture, ethnos, and national mentality based on the anthropocentric paradigm. The object of this field is language and culture, and the subject is linguistic units that show cultural semantics.

Creators, who are not separated from the environment in which they live, use dialect-specific words to embody this environment in their works, in order to portray life convincingly and vividly. The words specific to the dialects express the belonging to the region and add charm to the work and aesthetic pleasure to the reader.

Dialect is considered to be elements of the national language, outside the norms of the literary language. Therefore, such elements are not used in scientific, official and journalistic ways. But they are used to a certain standard in ordinary speech and artistic style. Elements of dialect used in the artistic style of the writer serves its stylistic-aesthetic purpose. In particular, emphasizing the hero's belonging to a certain region in an artistic work, creating a local color, helps to draw a realistic picture of life. Each region communicates through a specific dialect. Among them, the majority of Khorezm oasis residents communicate in the Oghuz dialect. Even when there are some subtle differences between the dialects and the concepts expressed in the literary language, the writer may prefer the dialect word.

Amon Matjon can also show the unique vocabulary of our dialects, the sweet and charming words of the Khorezm people by using the language units specific to

Khorezm dialects in his works. As a proof of our words, we can quote a passage from the poet's poem “Arosat”:

*A child's first free bond, mother,
A beautiful baby born in the womb,
Don't crush it, it's a great grandpa.*

The word “baby” in the verses is related to the Khorezm dialect and is used in the literary language to mean a baby. In “Ardakhiva” work “Marsiya”, which occupies a special place in the poet's work, we can also find dialect elements:

*... Red Bethel is colorful,
The poplar is blowing leaves,
I need a crying baby
Didn't the mountains help?!
The world of give and take,
Uykhan, get power from water!*

The words found in the above verses are dialectal words and are used in the literary language as “you need”. This also serves to increase the aesthetic appeal of the work. Besides:

*... I don't know whose law is,
Whose grain is whose flour?
I know whose blood is mine
My son and daughter were shocked.*

Among the words expressed in verses, the word , which belongs to the Khorezm dialect, is used in our literary language as son. As we explore the works of Amon Matjon, we can learn about the dialect and culture of this place as well as reading his works. As an example of the values that show the national traditions and customs of the Khorezm oasis, we can mention Khorezm lazgi, and dances. It is these values that the poet reflected in his poems “Letter to my friend from Khorezm”:

*Siberia? Okay! they saw
Most of the streets:*

Look, they don't take it off even in summer

Chogirma is a big made of sheepskin; sheepskin headdress made of round shape; a cap with a picture in Khorezm and Karakalpakstan, made of fur.

Guppi - light or light cotton cloak; thick cotton coat, ton. This is a word for women's clothing, made of cotton and made of cotton, mainly intended for wearing

in the autumn and winter season. Guppy is a thick cotton outerwear. If we pay attention to the etymology of the word guppy, it was previously worn only by workers. Therefore, in some comments, it is also called workers' clothing. The words “chogirma” and “guppy” belong to the Khorezm dialect and have no equivalent in the literary language. By using these words, the poet greatly contributed to the enrichment of the literary language, harmonizing the local color.

As we study the works of Amon Matjon, it is not difficult to understand his skill in using words and how much experience he has. Analyzed our words are words specific to the Khorezm dialect. To sum up, regardless of the subject of the poet's poems, he sings and praises the essence of man, his inner feelings with all his heart. Dialect words in his poems serve to reflect the color of Khorezm, to make art and expression beautiful.

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